

Studies in Formation and Properties of Carbon-Sulphur Surface Complexes: Part III. Formation on Treatment of Charcoal with Sulphur and Sulphur Dioxide

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The interaction of charcoal with sulphur or sulphur dioxide at 600° results in the fixation of sulphur, partly by substitution of combined hydrogen and partly by addition at unsaturated sites. The combined sulphur in the former case can be recovered as hydrogen sulphide and carbon disulphide and in the latter case also as sulphur dioxide on high temperature treatment in nitrogen. However, a certain amount of the combined sulphur cannot be recovered even at 1200°.

The chemical interaction of active carbons¹, coals² and carbon blacks^{3,4} with sulphur has been shown to involve fixation of 15-25% sulphur in 500-600° temperature range and 2-3% in 1000-1100° temperature range. It has been suggested that in the case of coals², sulphur is fixed in replacement of combined hydrogen and that in the case of carbon blacks^{3,4} it is fixed by addition giving rise to c-s-c- or c-s-s-c- groups. The interaction of carbons with sulphur dioxide from the point of view of chemisorption of sulphur has received far little attention⁵. There is a possibility for the simultaneous chemisorption of sulphur and oxygen in this case. It is also of interest to know if formation of a carbon-sulphur complex precedes the formation of carbon disulphide during these treatments just as formation of a loose carbon-oxygen complex is believed⁶ to precede the formation of carbon dioxide in combustion.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sugar and coconut charcoals prepared and deashed as before⁷ were used as such as well as after outgassing at 400, 700, 1060 and 1200°, in the manner described earlier⁸.

Treatment with sulphur: Charcoal (1 g. oven-dried at 120°) was mixed with 5 g. of sulphur (C.P.) in a small pestle and mortar and the mixture placed in a thick-walled pyrex glass tube (18" × 3" (4)) and heated in a tube furnace (15" × 1") to 600° for three hours. These conditions had been worked out in preliminary experiments for getting maximum fixation of sulphur. Hydrogen sulphide evolved during the interaction was estimated iodimetrically.

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Treatment with sulphur dioxide: Sulphur dioxide prepared by treating sodium metabisulphite (B.D.H. C.P.) with dilute sulphuric acid (C.P.) and dried by passing through calcium chloride tubes, was led at the rate of 3 lit./hr. for 8 hours, over 10 g. charcoal heated to 600° in the silica tube in the manner described above.

The treated products in either case were allowed to cool in the same atmosphere and then withdrawn and washed exhaustively first with water and then with carbon disulphide in the Soxhlet extractor for a week (10 hrs. a day).

Estimation of combined sulphur: The combined sulphur in a few samples was estimated first by Eschka's method⁹ and the results obtained were compared with those obtained from the amount of hydrogen sulphide evolved on heating 0.5 g. in a current of hydrogen at 1000° for 4 hours. The values obtained by the two methods were close to one another. The second method was followed in most of the determinations.

Bromine value: The amount of bromine fixed, as a measure of surface unsaturation, of the various samples of charcoal, before as well as after treatment, was determined as described earlier⁷.

Desorption of sulphur: Desorption of the combined sulphur was studied by heating the treated materials in a current of nitrogen at increasing temperatures upto 1200° in the manner described before¹⁰.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of interaction with sulphur at 600° are presented in Table I. The amount of sulphur fixed is seen to decrease with decrease in the initial hydrogen content of charcoal

TABLE I

Interaction of charcoal of varying hydrogen content with sulphur at 600°.

Sample	Hydrogen content (m.c./g.)			Hydrogen sulphide evolved (m.c./g.)	Sulphur fixed (m.c./g.)	Bromine value after heating at 600° (m.c./g.)	
	Initial	Final	Decrease			In the absence of sulphur	In the presence of sulphur.
Sugar charcoal original	33.9	18.3	15.6	14.8	12.4	3.1	0.5
—do—outgassed at 400°	32.8	17.7	15.1	14.3	11.1	3.3	0.2
—do— " " 700	25.8	18.5	7.3	5.4	7.3	3.5	nil
—do— " " 1000	11.7	9.6	2.1	2.0	4.0	3.7	nil
—do— " " 1200	10.2	9.3	0.9	0.2	3.2	3.7	0.4
Coconut charcoal original	28.8	14.7	14.1	14.7	13.5	3.4	nil
—do—outgassed at 400	28.2	14.3	13.9	13.0	10.5	3.5	nil
—do— " " 700	15.3	10.1	5.2	4.9	8.4	3.5	nil
—do— " " 1000	9.3	8.2	1.1	0.6	4.8	3.8	nil
—do— " " 1200	6.4	5.9	0.5	0.2	3.1	3.7	0.4

9. W. W. Scott, 'Standard Methods of Chemical Analysis', D. Van Nostrand Company, Inc., N.Y. p. 906 (1938).

10. B. R. Puri, *et al.*, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, (1966) in Press.

The amount of hydrogen sulphide evolved is approximately equivalent to that of hydrogen eliminated during treatment. However, the amount of sulphur fixed except in original and 400°-degassed charcoals is appreciably higher. At the same time the bromine value, which is an index of surface unsaturation, decreases considerably for every sample. It appears highly probable, therefore, that sulphur is fixed partly by substitution for surface hydrogen and partly by addition at unsaturated sites. In the case of 1000°- and 1200°-outgassed charcoals the amount of sulphur fixed is almost equal to fall in the bromine value. It appears that, in these cases, sulphur is fixed almost exclusively by addition at unsaturated sites and may be present as c-s-c or c-s-s-c groups³.

It is also seen that each charcoal retains an appreciable amount of hydrogen even after exhaustive treatment with sulphur. This hydrogen is held probably within the interior of carbon granules and is not easily accessible to sulphur atoms.

The amount of sulphur fixed on treatment with sulphur dioxide is seen (Table II) to be even greater than that fixed on treatment with sulphur in most of the samples. There is evidence again that the fixation of sulphur takes place by addition at unsaturated sites as well as by substitution of hydrogen. An appreciable amount of oxygen was also chemisorbed. It is seen to come off on outgassing at 1200° partly as carbon dioxide and partly as sulphur dioxide. There was also considerable loss in weight of charcoal due to gassification of carbon (column 6).

TABLE II

Interaction of the various samples of charcoal with sulphur dioxide at 600°.

Sample	Sulphur fixed (m.c./g)	Oxygen fixed and evolved on outgassing as (m.c./g)			Loss in weight due to gassification of carbon g./100g.	Bromine value after heating at 600° (m.c./g)	
		CO ₂	SO ₂	Total		In the absence of sulphur	In the presence of sulphur
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Sugar charcoal original	17.0	9.7	2.7	6.4	46.3	3.1	nil
—do—outgassed at 400°	16.6	9.5	2.4	5.9	45.5	3.3	nil
—do— " " 700	10.8	—	—	—	23.2	3.5	nil
—do— " " 1000	5.4	0.7	1.0	1.7	21.0	3.7	0.2
—do— " " 1200	3.5	0.4	0.8	1.2	20.3	3.7	nil
Coconut charcoal original	14.7	2.2	4.3	6.5	40.6	3.4	nil
—do— outgassed at 400	11.9	1.8	4.0	5.8	39.8	3.5	nil
—do— " " 700	9.7	—	—	—	18.7	3.5	nil
—do— " " 1000	4.2	0.8	0.8	1.6	13.7	3.8	nil
—do— " " 1200	2.6	0.5	0.4	0.9	12.0	3.7	0.9

The results obtained on heating in nitrogen, at different temperatures, one of the samples of charcoal after treatment with either sulphur or sulphur dioxide, are given in Table III. It is seen that in the case of sulphur-treated material, the combined sulphur is recovered as hydrogen sulphide (presumably by combination with residual hydrogen) and carbon disulphide. In the case of sulphur dioxide-treated material the combined sulphur is seen to be desorbed only in small amounts as hydrogen sulphide because very little hydrogen was retained in these samples. A much larger amount of sulphur is now stripped off as carbon disulphide. However, a small fraction of sulphur is retained in each case even on heating at 1200°.

TABLE III

Description of combined sulphur on heating in a current of nitrogen at different temperatures

400°—outgassed sugar charcoal treated with sulphur				
Temperature	Sulphur evolved as (m.c./g)		Sulphur retained (m.c./g.)	
	H ₂ S	CS ₂		
600°	1.3	nil	9.0	
800	3.5	nil	6.8	
1000	5.0	2.4	3.3	
1200	5.1	4.0	1.8	
400°—outgassed coconut charcoal treated with sulphur				
Sulphur fixed=10.5 m.c./g.				
600°	0.5	nil	9.1	
800	2.7	0.5	6.8	
1000	4.5	3.0	2.9	
1200	5.0	3.4	1.6	
400°—outgassed sugar charcoal treated with sulphur dioxide				
Sulphur fixed=16.6 m.c./g.				
	Sulphur evolved as (m.c./g.)			Sulphur retained (m.c./g.)
	H ₂ S	SO ₂	CS ₂	
600°	1.2	0.9	0.8	13.3
800	1.4	1.1	3.4	10.2
1000	2.1	1.2	7.8	4.6
1200	2.7	1.2	10.3	1.8
400°—outgassed coconut charcoal treated with sulphur dioxide				
Sulphur fixed=11.9 m.c./g.				
600°	0.7	1.7	nil	9.1
800	0.8	1.9	0.4	8.7
1000	1.8	2.0	3.2	4.6
1200	2.9	2.0	5.4	1.9

Some of the structures arising out of the fixation of sulphur on charcoal surface have been represented¹¹ as:

the two forms existing in equilibrium with one another as shown. It appears that when charcoal is deficient in hydrogen, the equilibrium, on heating in nitrogen, shifts more to the right, facilitating the formation and liberation of carbon disulphide. It appears also

that the chemisorption of sulphur by carbon on treatment with sulphur vapours or sulphur dioxide precedes formation of carbon-disulphide just as chemisorption of oxygen is believed to precede formation of oxides of carbon in combustion⁶.

A small amount of sulphur in the case of sulphur dioxide treated material was found to come off as sulphur dioxide showing that some sulphur dioxide also gets chemisorbed as such during the treatment. This is not unexpected due to the unsaturated nature of the gas and its tendency to form coordinate compounds.

The chemisorption of sulphur dioxide in appreciable amounts, as reported in this paper, and that of chlorine¹² and oxygen¹³ reported earlier, indicate possibilities of using charcoal as a catalyst for several reactions involving interaction of these gases with one another as well as with some other similar molecular species.

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